

**Topic- The Journey of an Introvert in Human Society:
Nisha in *Sultry Days***

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Abstract: The present research paper is going to deal with the introvert trait of personality, as propounded by Carl Jung, a psychologist, in the protagonist, Nisha. And in contrast, stands Dev (God) as an extrovert, but the focus is on Nisha, who explores the society through her introvert thinking and comes up with an accurate sketch of the society in which she lives and shares her physical and emotional space to her readers. This research paper examines the introvert spectrum which Shobha De has worked upon, consciously or unconsciously.

The very first question that bangs on the mind is why this title “The Journey of an Introvert in Human Society”. Actually, it is the scheme that Shobha De, a versatile author, adopts to set up the whole story of her novel where the heroine observes the society; its ingredients that are the people, the events, the actions and so on. She, being a part of it, has to indulge in the ongoing of the plot, along with her feelings, her reaction and thoughts, and eventually has to change, but then she being an observer, has to observe with an objective point of view, while she is observing the whole scenario.

Shobha De's present novel *The Sultry Days* emerged in 1994 after *Starry Nights* (1989), *Socialite Evenings* (1989), *Sisters* (1992). Shobha De's heroines; Asha Rani (*Starry Nights*) comes from a small town near Bombay and becomes sweetheart of millions, Karuna (*Socialite Evenings*) from middle class family, Anjali from a conservative family, Mallika (*Sisters*) belongs to a very rich family, then comes Nisha, our present heroine from a well to do family. In her earlier novels, the protagonist lives in the midst of the society becomes a part of its actions and observes the world around her and even moulds with its changing pattern, so does Nisha. But this time there is a little twist: Nisha judges herself an 'introvert' in the very beginning and it becomes clear to the reader that she will be guiding her/him with her insight, whether it be the other characters or their actions in the plot. While she is watching, she is just following the patterns of the human society like a catalyst or an enzyme, getting involved and yet getting unaffected as does an introvert.

Nisha's observations stage the whole show. The lead character is expected to be the most active soul in the story/plot, actually, the whole story revolves around him/her but the thoughts, ideas and analysis of the other characters, and the events remain far away from the readers. The author has no means to get involved into the psychological being of the characters. Compared to ancient human society, the modern human society is full of people, then to produce a hero or a heroine of *Hamlet* or *Cleopatra* type seems quite unrealistic. No battles are to be fought on the battlefields. We are left with the battles to be fought among relations, minds, passions and emotions. These can be better observed by an introvert; a silent observer, keen to participate in the very existence of this universe but does not want to be a part of it action. And thus, Shobha De gives Nisha in *Sultry Days*. In a podcast "Cyrus Says- Insatiable: The Hunger for Life w/ Shobha De" she accepts that her 'books are very conversational. They are

talking to the reader.’ Thus, when we read *Sultry Days*, Nisha is actually taking the reader in confidence while disclosing her heart, and all that she has felt while moving through space and time in her society.

And that is why defining the term “*introvert*” becomes so important because it is not just a word in general sense, rather a complete psychological concept given by **Carl Jung (1923)**. Carl Jung, a pioneering Swiss psychoanalyst and psychiatrist of the 20th century. In his classic book *Psychological Types*, Jung identified extroverts as “directing an outward flow of personal energy to the social environment” and introverts as “directing an inward flow of personal energy focused on internal factors” (Walker, 2021, p. 160).

In *Psychological Types (1921)* Jung presents his Theory of Psychological Typology. According to this theory individuals reveal regular patterns of actions, cognition, and personality traits. These can be categorized into six pairs of opposites as identified by Jung that define human psyche. They include:

- Two primary attitude orientations: Introversion - Extraversion
- Four primary functions in two pairs of opposites: Thinking -Feeling, and Intuition- Sensation,.

Thus, these six orientations and functions combine to form eight possible personality types (Jung, 1921). A brief indication of each type is as follows.

- Extraverted Thinking Principled, idealistic, objective, rational.
- Introverted Thinking Influenced by ideas, independent, often fearful of intimacy.

- Extraverted Feeling Adaptive, relating well to the external.
- Introverted Feeling Sympathetic, pleases others, may be dependent, reserved.
- Extraverted Sensation Realistic, concrete, pleasant and friendly.
- Introverted Sensation Calm and passive, restrained, controlled and controlling.
- Extraverted Intuition Enterprising, outgoing, can be irresponsible.
- Introverted Intuition Mystical, dreamer and artist. Can be obsessive.

Jung's model still serves as the basis for a range of different psychometric tools. In 1913 he published 'A Contribution to the Study of Psychological Types' where Jung argued that there were two contrary movements of the libido; Extraversion, with interest given to the outer world, and Introversion, implying a devaluation of the object world. These represented two habitual orientation attitudes towards the world; an outward movement of interest towards the object or a movement away from the object to the subject's own psychological processes. Introversion characterized defences against emotional isolation. Internal thoughts and personal exploration typically energize introverts.

The present novel *Sultry Days is De's* fifth novel set in Mumbai. It is a realistic romantic story which begins in the college and explores the life of youngsters while they are handing their careers, struggling with the lifestyles set by their parents, their education and then by the society. The life of upper middle class and that of the lower middle class is the main focus in which the thinking, ideology, and life, as such, is dealt with the youth struggling to explore the real meaning of relationship in life. When Nisha appears, she is already in college engrossed in thoughts of Dev/ God, who is exact opposite to her. This lead character, Nisha, is presented as an introvert while her counter-part is also there, an extreme extrovert, in her boyfriend, Dev, who is also called as 'God';

“God wasn’t at all what I’d expect him to be. He spoke with a vernac accent and smoked smelly beedies. He also changed my (Nisha’s) name the moment we were introduced.... It’s a ridiculous name from now on, you’ll be my intoxicant, my *nasha*.”(p.1)

Nisha accepted the name given to her by Dev, though she did not like it. She is presented as calm, passive, ready to please others, and restrained. She actually is least interested in taking action. She is at peace with whatever is happening around her. She is a silent observer.

....I (Nisha) wasn’t impressed....But didn’t dare say anything by way of protest. One didn’t do that with God.”

Dev does not come from a polished society like Nisha’s. There is a mixed emotion on part of Nisha towards him.

“I’d never really liked him but I must admit to a deep fascination. A sort of infatuation towards him that simultaneously attracted and repelled.” (p.1)

Gradually, as the story moves on, Dev enters a world of poetry and lives in a world of imagination where everything that can be bought with money is meant not to be bought by him. But he depends on others to offer him these things. Nisha takes a job in an advertizing company. Again, a contrast is set here; one goes with pure imagination, the other, i.e. Nisha goes in the field of planned imagination, which suits the commercial world. So there is analysis of

the two field of life; one is natural while other is materialistic. While pursuing their careers they come across people from different backgrounds and different professions. Thus, there is introvert heroine Nisha who peeps into the life, and activities of these people and the reader gets a varied view of the society around him/her.

Nisha's personality is developed to the readers through her own self-observation. She is striving towards wholeness of her '*self*', in terms of Carl Jung. Jung identified an introverts as "directing an inward flow of personal energy focused on internal factors" (Walker, 2021, p. 160). This trait is very obvious in Nisha which is going to be analyzed further.

Like an introvert she is fearful of intimacy:

'Once I'd ducked into the library. I felt safe. I felt safe. I could dive into my books and pretend to read. I could strike my favorite pose and not be found out....I fitted in here just like the other into the other introverts and wallflowers around me. I didn't know why I felt awkward in company. There wasn't anything particularly wrong with me, do you couldn't know it by the question that was most often ask of me.

(p.2)

Nisha, the heroine, is well acquainted by her person/ psyche. That is not a case of worry for her but the society; not only the society, the very close relatives, even her parents are not ready to accept her as she is. Thus, she further investigates her psyche by telling about the reaction of her parents, who early in the morning, for god knows what reason had not yet accepted her as she is, after so many years staying with their own daughter. Nisha observes:

“It used to start first saying in the morning. The moment I walked into the dining room for a cup of tea, my mother would look at my face and anxiously and ask, “What's wrong?” (p.2)

Yes, of course, a mother is concerned about the looks of her daughter but there is acceptance on her part, in Nisha's case it fails.

“I'd want to yell, ‘NOYHING’, but that wasn't done....Father would follow shortly...”Is baby up yet?” And then, on seeing me that irritating question, “What's wrong?” (p.2)

Further, she observes:

“Was it my expression? Did I looked troubled? In pain? Depressed? Maybe it was the worth mark of mine.... I was born with worry lines brows....They grew darker and gave the impression that I was constantly frowning or scrolling....the school teachers also remarked ‘she needs to cheer up and take more interest in extra -curricular activities.(p.2)

It is in fact difficult to live with people who are ready to accept you as you are but practically fail to understand it and try to change the person according to their own choices. They even fail to see the truth that they themselves have been already accepted as they are. Nobody can change the physical buildup, psychological qualities or mannerism a person is borne with, and it is too hard to

overcome them. Then why, the space that Nisha should enjoy with her introversion not given to her? In terms of Jung, Nisha is striving to maintain a balance between opposing qualities while at the same time actively seeking its own development or as he called it, *individuation*.

An introvert possesses a minimal of friends around to share their thoughts and emotions. They “are often more thoughtful in their social activities. They prefer smaller, close-knit networks. ...introversion promotes small heterophilic networks” (Tohver, 2021, p. 164). Nisha has a best friend who also leaves her when Nisha gets involved with God or actually she is replaced by Dev, an awkward fellow, who is all-acceptable with his

“....smelly beedies” (p.1) with “Matted locks- which I (Nisha) was sure where full of lice-nests and other creepy crawlies. One hand of his was invariably engaged in scratching. The hand didn't stop at the head.... his hand tore inside his filthy shirt and scratched up a bloody pool. It travelled down to his groin, up to his armpit, right around to his back.” (p.1)

Throughout the novel, Dev is the only close friend Nisha sustains with until his breadth. This fellow was a God to the college fellow, especially girls, “who paid for his special *chai* and even offered to subsidize haircuts” (p.1) Nisha nourished a sort of infatuation towards him that simultaneously attracted and repelled. In the first line of the novel Nisha thinks, “God wasn't at all what I'd expected him to be” (p.2) but the next moment she is not ready to protest when he charged her name to *Nasha*.

“One didn't do that with God.” (p.1)

She though had reached college “she had not learned to live with it-- ‘the frown.’”

“And often, when I (Nisha) catch sight of myself in a mirror I’m insulted. I nearly ask myself, “What’s wrong?” (p.3)

In the next line it becomes clear why Nisha developed an attraction towards God/Dev

“Go was the only one who thought my frown was ‘cute’. “I like it *yaar*”, he told me, and for that moment at least, ‘I am sure it disappeared.” (p.3)

And God was the fellow who had straightforward mindset.

“Look, I don't want any of your fancy stuff. It does not impress me. If you want to hang around, it’s OK. But don't expect me to change-*wange* for you I am what I am - take it or leave it.” (p.4)

Here she identifies with him as she also believes in having a space for herself in the society as she is and not as others wish her to be. Nisha wished to hang around him so was ready to bow down. “I learnt quickly that I had to bury whatever little ego and pride I had...” (p.3)

She accepts that she had silent crushes without letting the partner even know about it. But she finds in God what was lacking in her, so for him,

“I still don’t know and cannot explain where I got the courage to go for God in such an obvious way.” (p.5)

“Even when God was talking about another girl in his life she did not speak out her love for him and only kept thinking.” what was he saying I would die without him I would go mad with grief how could he feel that way when I am so happy?”

But then everything was settled and she was for him. According to Walker and Tohver, (2021) an introvert characteristically is comfortable with ‘an organized and routine lifestyle’ and we find Nisha, at the very beginning, settled with a job in a mediocre ad agency, as she wished nothing else to do. She is not ready to take challenges. She looks for the safer side of an action, do what is best to do to keep herself tension free, and let life keep rolling without any jerks. Challenges are not her way. She accepts life as it comes to her and she just creates a space for herself in the society in which she survives.

Whenever God met with any offensive situation with a female, he would say,

“That female has problems. She looks frustrated. She needs a good screw.” (p.11)

Nisha never liked the attitude of his towards the women, but then that was what he was, so this was understood between them that they have to live, as they are if they want to survive and wish to go along in the society on their own.

At another instance, she clearly avoids over stimulating situation and is quite passive when Dev hardly gives importance to her passion for red shoes. Hers is a very introvert passive reaction:

‘I had a shoe fetish--- and still do,’ when Nisha ‘stops at a sandal store to gaze with longing at the gorgeous new styles. He (Dev) impatiently prodded her to move on, ‘Forget it *yaar*. You don’t need any chappal-wappal. Come on; let’s go get me an umbrella. I got drenched waiting for you to show up.’

“I didn’t dare tell him that one of my secret childhood longings was to own a cupboard full of shoes in every conceivable colour. Particularly red.”

On her fifth birthday, she ‘plucked up courage to ask my mother for them. But Mother being Mother thought in terms of ‘wasteful expenditure.’ (pp.12-13)

She could not even express herself when she is financially independent and free to buy her choice of shoes. It’s a height of passivity when an introvert is not ready to claim what she can do very easily. Yet another instance:

God was even more sarcastic than usual about the Maldives trip. ‘What are you going there for?...You aren’t a model or a starlet.’

Nisha remains calm and replies, “Why don’t we change the subject and talk about you?”...

But Dev bursts out. “The very fact that you have to ask me all these questions shows how indifferent you are to my life. It is all you, you, you...”

But Nisha retains her composure and handles the situation,

“Don’t be unpleasant, Dev, What’s the matter? Broke?”...”Then why are we fighting?”....

“Dev...you haven’t played your flute for such a long time. Why don’t we spend a quiet evening catching up and listening to your melody?”(p.98)

Nisha is a quiet observer and through her, the reader penetrates the life and thoughts of all the characters in the plot. She engages quiet, reserved behaviors to maintain the level of arousal. This is what she does throughout the novel. She tries to maintain her composure, that way it becomes easy to read the thoughts of the other people around her and how she could respond without getting out of her safety cell. When Nisha's mother got a hint that her husband was having an extra-marital affair, she lost her brains and started behaving strangely.

‘Mummy was talking to herself and rearranging the contents of her dressing-table for the five--hundredth time. I didn't pay attention any longer...Any more mother-daughter combination at firm parties was out of question....I couldn't bear the atmosphere.’ (p.85)

There is another important trait very common in introverts that they experience heightened sensitivity when processing stimuli:

When God asked her,

“How would you like to become a goddess?” and revved the engine.... I (Nisha) yelled over the sound of BEST buses scraping past our ears...” Are you asking me to marry you?” I must have really hollering....I tapped on the fiberglass (of helmet) dome covering his head....I couldn't resist a tummy squeeze. I would have bitten his ear if it hadn't been covered.” (p.85)

As an objective explorer, she keeps objectively observing people and events without indulging in their plans of life. And she pulls herself together without getting hurt. This is the best way that she adopts to save her being in the society

which impounds upon the human beings and forces them to keep them changing and fall in a pattern that suits better for its existence.

God was always there in her life but shared a separate space that nobody could occupy. God never changed his clumsy ways and Nisha never asked him to do so. They accepted each other as they were and that is the reason why they survived the changing world, until he was shot by Yashwantbhai:

“I thought he was dying. He looked so weak and helpless. As I sat on an uncomfortable, bug-ridden wooden stool at his bedside, my mind couldn’t stop itself from going into flashbacks. It was just like in the movies. An anxious woman, once thwarted, sitting at the bedside of a man she loves, hoping against hope that he wouldn’t die on her....I was longing to hold this impossible man in my arms and whisper to him, ‘Dear God ...be mine.’” (p.225)

And he died in the hospital.

Like a protagonist should do, she, the *sutradhar* of the novel, presents certain details that were very important about certain characters, like Bubbly, Chandni, Kawla, Iqwal, and so on, who are important to show what a society has in its infrastructure.

Our evolving understanding of what it means to be an introvert vs. an extrovert offers many insights into our personalities and how they influence our thinking and behavior (Larsen et al., 2017). This fact has been very well used and explored by Shobha De in her present novel. Though *Sultry Days* is what Shobha De wants it to be; a child of her imagination, she has drawn characters from her surroundings in which we come across all sorts of people we meet in our life. Nisha explores the life and actions of people around her that build up

the whole story. She appears to be a silent observer evolving gradually with the plot but her main character never undergoes a drastic change. As Tohver says, “Individuals typically show great variation in their extraversion–introversion tendency across their lifespan” (p. 164). During our career, we may develop more extrovert tendencies out of necessity to meet the needs of our role. At the same time, as we age, we typically find that extraversion declines, and there is a rise in introversion (Tohver, 2021). Nisha appears to manipulate her actions to tune up with the demands of time and society and also her career but at the bottom of her heart, she is what she had been in the beginning.

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